

SINGLE-SHEAR BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL GLASS-FIBER REINFORCED POLYESTER PRODUCED BY THE RTM TECHNIQUE

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SUMMARY

Single-shear tests were performed at a strain rate of about 0.0005 s^{-1} , using a torsional loading system, in order to study the effect of fiber orientation in multidirectional glass-fiber reinforced polyester specimens prepared from laminates of different stacking sequence, fabricated using the RTM technique at a fiber volume fraction of about 61%.

Keywords: Novel single-shear test. Torsional loading system. Multi-ply glass fiber reinforced polyester composite. Resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique.

INTRODUCTION

The present worldwide development programs in plastic composites are leading to materials with extremely high structural strength and modulus-to-weight ratio. The efficient and safe use of these materials in structures requires a full characterization of their mechanical properties under various service conditions. On the other hand, the chosen manufacturing process often plays an important role in achieving the required final properties, and in reducing the overall cost of the reinforced plastic product [1, 2]. For fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), many manufacturing routes currently exist. These routes are either open or closed moulding processes which employ various fabrication techniques such as hand lay-up, spraying, vacuum and pressure bag moulding, hot and cold press moulding, injection and transfer moulding, filament winding, centrifugal casting, and pultrusion. Resin transfer moulding (RTM) processes are believed to provide significant cost savings potential relative to the traditional stacking method and are therefore gaining attention in industry [3].

In the current investigation the resin transfer moulding (RTM) method has been used to produce a laminate with multidirectional fiber orientation in one step, instead of the stacking method which has been used in many previous investigations, in order to increase the fiber volume fraction and correspondingly the laminate strength. Specimens prepared from such laminates of glass-fiber reinforced polyester were then tested in direct shear in order to elucidate the effect of fiber orientation on the stress-strain quasi-static behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials and Specimens

Glass-fiber reinforced polyester (GFRP) plates were locally prepared in the laboratory. Continuous roving E glass (BT 89 AX8 2400 J-BP 7AD 85716) manufactured by Owens Corning Fiber Glass (GB) Ltd, and polyester resin (SIROPOL 8321 LS), supplied by Saudi Industrial Resins Ltd, were used as fiber and matrix, respectively. Properties of the fiber and resin, as given by the suppliers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of fiber and resin, as given by the suppliers

PROPERTY	FIBER	RESIN	PROPERTY	FIBER	RESIN
Density (Kg/ m ³)	2540	1200	Tensile Strength (MPa)	1900	50
Specific Heat (J/Kg C)	711	2000	Tension to Break (%)	4.5	3.5
Thermal Exp. Coeff. (10 ⁻⁶ C ⁻¹)	5	100	Compressive Strength (MPa)	1200	140
Young's modulus (MPa)	70000	3700	Compression to Break (%)	4	

The Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) technique, shown in Fig. 1, was employed to manufacture the GFRP plates. This technique was chosen to overcome the disadvantages associated with the hand lay-up technique, thus guaranteeing: (a) an almost zero percentage of trapped air bubbles, (b) a constant fiber/resin ratio throughout the plate specimen, and (c) a homogeneous laminate due to the elimination of rich layers of resin between the plies.

Special wooden moulds were prepared and used to produce laminates with 5 layers of unidirectional glass fiber, each layer having a thickness of 1mm. Some of the steps involved are shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b), which are self-explanatory. A layer of Gelcoat was used to guarantee a smooth skin for the mould, while polyester resin mixed with Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide (MEKP) as catalyst and Cobalt Naphthenate as accelerator was poured into the mould under a 5 m head pressure, and assisted by vacuum from a vent point. Detailed description of the manufacturing process is given in references [4, 5, 6].

(a) Dressing in 1st direction

(b) Dressing in 2nd direction

Figure 1: Principle of RTM technique Figure 2: Steps in preparing the laminated plate

Specimens with various fiber orientations and constant fiber volume fraction of 61% were prepared in strip form from the composite plates using a pneumatic saw (Fig. 3). For direct-shear testing, two specimens were glued by Araldite epoxy cement to two holders and tested at the same time in the torsional system. Specimens in different configurations were used (Fig. 4), namely: pure resin, $(45,-45,0)_s$, $(60,-60,0)_s$, $(90,-30,30)_s$, $(0,60,-60)_s$, and $(0,90,45)_s$.

Figure 3: Specimens and holder shapes and dimensions (Dimensions are in mm)

Figure 4: Typical fiber directions in specimens tested in tension

(a) $(0,60,-60)_s$; (b) $(60,-60,0)_s$; (c) $(90,-30,30)_s$

Testing Apparatus and Procedures

The torsional system employed in the tests is shown schematically in Fig. 5. It consists of the following units mounted on two rigid beds: a central shaft, a rotational drive unit, a specimen mount, anti-frictional supports, a frictional clamp, and suitable instrumentation.

The central shaft consists of two collinear bars, input and output bars of 25 mm diameter, mounted on supports lined with cylindrical Teflon blocks to minimize frictional resistance during rotation. The specimen holders are illustrated in Fig. 3 (b). Two specimens were attached between two holders by means of Araldite epoxy cement. The gage length (h_3) was adjusted to 1.3 mm using a filler gage. After complete setting of the cement, the excess length of the specimens was trimmed, then the assembly sandwiched between the inner ends of the input and output bars, as shown in the inset of

Fig. 5. For direct-shear loading, the far end of the input bar is keyed to a rotational drive unit, while the far end of the output bar is rigidly fixed in a frictional clamp. The rotational drive unit consists of a 1 HP single phase electric motor having a fixed speed of 1440 rpm, a vee-belt reduction of 1:4, two compact speed reduction units of 1:30 fixed reduction ratio each, one speed reduction unit of 1:60 reduction ratio, and a gear box of 1:1, 1:1.6, 1:2, and 1:2.66 reduction ratios. In all tests, adjustments were made to obtain a specimen average shear strain rate of about 0.0022 s^{-1} .

Figure 5: Direct-shear test arrangement

To characterize the material shear behaviour in terms of stress-strain curves, two physical quantities need to be accurately measured continuously during the test, namely: the applied torque (T) and the twist angle (θ). The layout of the instrumentation used for this purpose is illustrated in Fig. 5 [7]. The angular displacement corresponding to the twist angle at the driving end of the input bar was measured by a direct current displacement transducer (DCDT). A small pulley was securely attached to the input bar and a thin nylon wire wound around it. One end of this wire was fastened to the pulley, and the other to the core of the DCDT. The applied torque was measured with strain gauge rosettes stuck on the output bar. During a test, the output signals of the DCDT and the strain-gauge bridge were fed to the horizontal and vertical channels of an x-y recorder, respectively. Examples are shown in Fig. 6. Each plot was calibrated to provide a stress-strain curve for the specimen, after properly accounting for the elastic deformation of the system.

The engineering direct-shear stress and strain could be calculated as follows. The strain gage signal plotted on the y-axis of the recorder was properly calibrated in terms of corresponding applied torque (T), while the DCDT signal plotted on the horizontal axis was translated into twist angle (θ). As mentioned above, the shear test was carried out

on two specimens at the same time. The specimen shear stress (τ) and shear strain (γ) were calculated with the following expressions:

$$\tau = T / (2 r h_1 h_2), \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma = \theta r / h_3$$

where r ($= 11.0$ mm) is the radius of the circle passing through the middle of the 2 specimens, h_1 ($= 4$ mm) is the specimen width, h_2 ($= 5$ mm) is its thickness, and h_3 ($= 1.3$ mm) its gauge length, as shown in Figs. 3 and 5.

Figure 6: Typical torque-angular displacement plots obtained during quasi-static direct-shear testing of various specimens

RESULTS

The shear stress-strain curves of all the tested laminates, as well as the resin, are collected together in Fig. 7. Also, the shear modulus, the ultimate shear stress and strain of all tested laminates under quasi-static shear loading are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Direct-Shear Test Results

<i>ORIENTATION</i>	<i>Shear Modulus (GPa)</i>	<i>Ultimate Shear Stress (MPa)</i>	<i>Ultimate Shear Strain (%)</i>
Pure Resin	4.228	40.1	1.2
(45, -45, 0) _s	5.44	41.0	1.5
(90, -30, 30) _s	5.44	42.75	1.86
(60, -60, 0) _s	3.78	59.5	2.9
(0, 90, 45) _s	5.44	78.0	2.3
(0, 60, -60) _s	5.44	88.2	2.46

Figure 7: Stress Strain curves for different laminates under direct shear

In Fig. 7, the stress-strain curve of pure resin illustrates that the maximum shear stress is associated with the rupture stress, which is equal to 40.1 MPa at ultimate strain of 1.2 %. The shear modulus obtained for pure resin equals approximately to 4.23 GPa. The shear stress-strain curve of the (45, -45, 0)_s laminate shows that the ultimate shear strain for this laminate increased to 1.5 % and the shear modulus increased to 5.44 GPa, higher than that for pure resin. The maximum stress is not highly affected, may be due to the slipping of the fibers against each other at 45 degree. On the other hand, the ultimate shear stress for the (60, -60, 0)_s laminate increased to 59.5 MPa and the corresponding ultimate strain reached 2.9 %. The shear stress-strain curve of the (90, -30, 30)_s laminate reaches the maximum stress value of 42.75 MPa at a strain of 1.86 %. The curve is bilinear up to the maximum stress, with an initial slope of 5.4 GPa up to 0.3 % strain, then a lower value up to maximum stress. The stress of the (0, 90, 45)_s laminate reaches its maximum value of 78 MPa at a strain equal to 2.3 %. When the stress level is equal to 30 MPa at 0.7 % strain, the slope of the curve changed from 5.4 GPa to 2.8 GPa. The ultimate stress of the (0, 60, 60)_s laminate is obtained at a shear strain of 2.46 %, and equals 88.2 MPa, corresponding to an increase of about 215 % when compared to the ultimate stress of pure resin. Also the ultimate strain increased to about double that of the pure resin. From the previous curves it is observed that the (0,60,-60)_s laminate has the highest shear failure resistance, while the (45,-45.0)_s and (90, -30, 30)_s laminates exhibit the lowest resistance.

It is seen that most of these laminates have the same initial linear response, where the slope equals to 5.44 GPa. The exception of this is for the (60.-60, 0)_s laminate which shows initial coincidence with the resin behaviour. The curves also show that there is always a change in the slope of the stress-strain curves for all the laminates. It is

believed that the changes in the slope are associated with successive plies failure within the laminate.

Results of quasi-static and dynamic testing of the laminates in question have reported recently elsewhere [8]. The strengths of all laminates as well as the pure resin are drawn in Fig. 8 in both quasi-static tension and shear, for comparison. It can be seen that most of the laminates has shear strength less than half its tensile strength. Also, it is shown that the highest tensile and shear strengths are obtained for the laminates that have zero degree orientation plies especially if they are the outer plies. The only exception of this is the (45,-45, 0)_s laminate which has the lowest shear strength. On the other hand, the presence of 90° plies as the outer plies results in laminates having poor tensile and shear strengths. Similar results for CFRP (T300/976) laminates were reported by Johnson and Chang [9] and McCartney [10]. From the figure it can be realized that the static shear strength is matrix-controlled which has been observed from the slope of the shear stress-strain curves of the tested laminates, whereas the static tensile strength is dominated by the fiber properties.

Figure 8: Tensile and shear strengths of the tested laminates under quasi-static loading.

CONCLUSIONS

This investigation into the quasi-static direct shear behaviour of glass fiber reinforced polyester laminates (E glass/polyester SIROPOL 8321 LS) produced by the RTM technique revealed the following:

- a) The resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique allows the achievement of a fiber volume fraction of 61 % and homogeneous laminated composites.
- b) The experimental shear results reveal that the initial shear modulus of elasticity is independent of the plies stacking sequence in the laminate, while the ultimate shear stress is highly affected by it.
- c) The 90° plies in the (90, 30,-30)_s laminate have a dominating effect on strength, whereby the laminate shows a decreasing shear strength, especially when these orientations are in the outer plies.
- d) The (45, -45, 0)_s laminate exhibits the lowest strength among all laminated composites. This laminate is not recommended for use in shear.
- e) The (0,60,-60)_s laminate exhibits the highest shear strength. Hence, it is recommended for use when a structure is subjected to shear loading.

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